

Teaching-Learning Strategies and Activities Employed by College Instructors in their Online and Face-to-face Classes

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ABSTRACT

The study presents a repertoire of teaching and learning activities employed by the School of Education faculty and students in the online and face-to-face classes. The field notes for the class observations of the SED faculty in their online classes in the AY 2021-2022 and the face-to-face class observations in the AY 2022-2023 were the empirical data on the teaching and learning activities employed. Thirty-four class observation results were analyzed as to what teaching strategies were used and what activities were employed in the lesson delivery. Descriptive data analysis was utilized from the excerpts of the lessons. Findings revealed that the prevailing strategy utilized in online and face-to-face instruction was the lecture method enhanced by varying techniques in its presentation. Often, the lecture-discussion method stands out as the joint strategy that integrates the ICT like the PPT, video clips, songs, stories, illustrations, and pictures. The categorization of the activities based on the teaching-learning theories showed that the teachers were more cognitivists in their approach, followed by the constructivists, then behaviorists. College teachers are more inclined to develop the cognitive skills of the students as these are reflected in their lesson objectives and in the manner of giving assessments.

Subject Area

**Teaching and Learning Strategies; Online Class;
Face-to-Face Class**

Keywords: *Teaching and Learning Activities, Teaching Strategies, Constructivist, Behaviorist, Cognitivist*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching is the process done by a teacher to transmit knowledge, know-how, and interpersonal skills to a student in an educational institution. It is the process of imparting knowledge or instructing someone to do something. It is attending to the students' needs, experiences, and feelings so that they can learn particular things or even beyond what is presented in schools. Teaching is closely related to learning, which is the student's activity of accumulating knowledge (Manuel Musial; Fabienne Pradere; André Tricot, 2012). The teaching process involves knowledge and includes different forms, such as values, manners, skills, behaviors, traditions, and stories (Hasa, 2017). Teaching is attending to people's needs, experiences, and feelings and making specific interventions to help them learn particular things. Good teaching is more than techniques. Good teaching 'comes from the identity and integrity of the teacher' (Palmer, 1998). It is how people experience enthusiasm, care, knowledge, interest in, and concern for people. Jackie Beere (2012) argued that teachers must be present as people in the classroom or learning environment.

Learning is gaining and retaining the knowledge given. The learning process begins when one gains a new experience, whether reading a new word, listening to someone explain a concept, or trying a new method for solving a problem (Cherry, Kendra, 2022). *Learning* is a relatively lasting behavior change that is the result of experience. It is acquiring information, knowledge, behaviors, skills, values, or preferences. *Learning* is an ongoing process throughout life and is not confined to the classroom. Learning continues throughout people's lives (Hasa, 2017) – from birth to death. People learn starting from babyhood, and as they grow up, they learn many other skills. This type of learning happens through observing, experimenting, and experiencing.

Teaching and learning are parts of the broader concept of education. Teaching and learning are essential processes linked to acquiring knowledge, values, traditions, skills, behaviors, etc. These two processes are at the two ends of the knowledge acquisition process. At San Isidro College School of Education, the faculty members are observed in their classes every semester. One of the main components in the teaching-learning process is teaching effectiveness, which is visible in how teachers and students engage in the different activities. Varied teaching and learning activities are exhibited during the class delivery. The procedures and how the teachers deliver these activities are essential to students' learning. These crucial aspects have an excellent bearing on what and how the students accumulate knowledge on the lesson. Therefore, these activities must be sorted out to examine their relevance to the student's learning and to the teacher's consideration as to which strategies could have a good impact on students' learning.

This study explored the different teaching-learning strategies and activities the teachers and students engage in during online and face-to-face classes. It also categorized whether the teaching-learning activities leaned towards the constructivist, behaviorist, or cognitivist approach.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Teaching and learning theories are organized principles explaining how individuals acquire, retain, and recall knowledge. Knowing these theories can help educators better understand how learning occurs. Teaching and learning generally highlight the theories of constructivists, behaviorists, and cognitivist.

Constructivist Theory

Dewey, Piaget, Vygotsky, Gagne, and Bruner popularized constructivist theory. Constructivism is based on the premise that individuals construct their perspectives of the world from individual experiences and internal knowledge. Constructive theory is vital in introducing teaching and learning. This theory derives from students' existing knowledge and skills. Learning is based on how individuals interpret and create the meaning of their experiences. By applying a constructivist approach, students synthesize new understanding with their prior knowledge and learning (James Kelly, 2012).

Teachers set up problems for students, guide them to inquire about them, and monitor their exploration. In this strategy, students must learn from their exploration after synthesizing raw data, primary sources, and interactive material. This process helps students to evolve knowledge. Constructivist approaches are practical with learners of all ages. Examples and applications of constructivism include case studies, research projects, problem-based learning, brainstorming, collaborative learning/group work, discovery learning, and simulations. Gagne's nine instruction steps include gaining the students' attention, informing the learners of the objectives, stimulating recall of prior learning, presenting the content, providing learning guidance, eliciting performance, providing feedback, assessing the performance, and enhancing retention and transfer.

Behaviorist Theory

J. B. Watson and B. F. Skinner are the main contributors to behaviorist learning theory. The behaviorist's theory focuses on observable behaviors and discounts any independent mental activity. According to this theory, learning occurs only when individuals can see the results. This is because behaviorists are interested in seeing a behavior change. Moreover, the acquisition of new behavior is based on environmental conditions. Learning begins with a cue or stimulus from the environment. Teachers use behaviorism when they reward or punish students' behaviors. Examples and applications of behaviorist learning theory include drill/rote work, repetitive practice, giving incentives/bonus points, verbal reinforcements, and establishing rules (Feder, 2022).

Cognitivist Theory

The proponents of the cognitivist theory are Jean Piaget (mental development is progressive), Jerome Bruner (theory of learning by discovery), David Ausubel (significant learning), Robert Gagne (levels of learning), and Howard Gardner (multiple intelligences) (Briceño, 2019). The cognitivists process information based on the thought process behind the behavior. The theory is based on the idea that humans process the information they receive, and the learner's mind is like a mirror from which new knowledge and skills are reflected (Kelly, 2012). Observing, taking instruction, and imitating the behavior of others help in learning more effectively. This specific learning results from watching, listening, experiencing, and touching. The robust mechanism of cognitive learning provides knowledge and goes well beyond simple imitation. Simply, it means the acquisition of knowledge using mental or cognitive processes. It is the process used for manipulating information 'in the head. In short, mental representations of physical objects and information processing are created through cognitive learning. Examples and applications of cognitive learning include classifying or chunking information, linking concepts, providing

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structure, real-world examples, discussions, problem-solving, analogies, imagery, pictures, and mnemonics.

Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of the study. The three theories of constructivists, behaviorists, and cognitivists influence the class's teaching and learning strategies and activities. Teaching involves imparting knowledge, whereas learning involves acquiring knowledge. This is the main difference between teaching and learning (Hasa, 2017). Figure 2 shows the difference between teaching and learning (Pediaa, 2022).

Figure 1.
Theories of Teaching and Learning

Teaching vs Learning	
Teaching	Learning
Teaching is the process of imparting knowledge and instruction	Learning is the acquisition of knowledge, behavior, skills, values, etc.
People can teach something to others even unconsciously	People learn throughout their lives either consciously or unconsciously
Teaching is always linked with learning and learners	One does not need to be taught to learn something

Source: www.PEDIAA.com

Figure 2.*Differentiation between Teaching and Learning***STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM**

The study explored the teaching and learning strategies and activities employed by the SED faculty in their classes from the Academic Years 2021-2022 and 2022-2023. It specifically answered the following:

1. What are the teaching and learning activities employed by the teacher and the students as they engaged in their lessons in their online and face-to-face classes?
2. How are these teaching and learning activities categorized based from the point of view of the constructivist, behaviorist, and the cognitivist?

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized the descriptive research method employing factual analysis of the teaching and learning strategies and activities observed during the class observations in their online classes in the 2nd semester of the academic year 2021-2022 and the face-to-face class observations during the first and second semester of the academic year 2022-2023. The descriptive analysis is factual because the data are based on observations of classroom lessons and discourses. The research locale is at San Isidro College (SIC), the only Catholic higher education in Malaybalay. The Commission duly accredits SIC on Higher Education (CHED) and the Department of Education (DepEd). It is also a member of the Catholic Educational Association of the Philippines (CEAP) and the Bukidnon Association of Catholic Schools (BUACS). From its humble beginnings in 1949, the school continues to provide quality Catholic Education where students adhere to its philosophy, vision, mission, goals and objectives, core values and graduate attributes.

During the academic year 2021-2022, 16 faculty were observed in their online class via Google Meet due to the COVID pandemic lockdown. In the academic year 2022-2023, when the school is implementing the full-swing face-to-face delivery, eight instructors were observed during the first semester, and ten instructors were observed during the second semester. A total of 35 recorded class observation results were analyzed regarding the strategies used and the activities employed. Extracted from the class observations were the topic and the strategies used, as well as the activities that were employed in the delivery of the lesson.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Teaching –Learning Activities and Strategies Employed in Online Classes

Matrix 1 illustrates the teaching and learning activities employed by the SED faculty in their online classes during the academic year 2021-2022 at the height of the pandemic lockdown. It is observed that the lecture teaching method was predominantly utilized and enhanced by other supporting techniques. PowerPoint presentation of the lecture was the dominant strategy used. Some teachers used video clips, music, stories, and narratives, games, pictures, and paintings to facilitate the lecture.

Matrix 1.

Teaching–learning strategies and activities employed by the faculty in their Online Class Observations during the 2nd semester of the academic year 2020-2021.

Teaching-Learning Strategies and activities observed during the class observation via Google Meet	
T-1	<p>Topic: Music Appreciation</p> <p>Strategies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">-Lecture using video clips-Audio listening to musical pieces of different music composition <p>Activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">-Teacher presented the video clip of Celine Dion on All by Myself and asked the students why Celine stopped in her singing as some point. She gave a brief story on the background of the music and why Celine stopped singing. She then gave a brief lecture on classical music on types of musical expression, rhythmic expression, lyrics over the music, and the way performers express themselves.-Teacher presented one video clip of another composition and asked the students the movement of the music. Every time she presents a video clip of the composition she asked the student their observations of the flow of the music, in terms of movement, tempo, notes played, expression. This she did with <i>Lyra angelica</i>, <i>Chopin's Nutcracker</i>, <i>The hole of the mountain king</i>, <i>Chopin's ballad</i>, etc. The teacher asked the students to listen, observed, and gave their analysis of the composition played based from her lecture. She usually gave the background of the music and narrates stories associated with this music. The stories are entertaining and it could elicit interest in the learners.
T-2	<p>Topic: Literary Technique</p> <p>Strategies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">-Lecture-discussion method using PowerPoint presentation online-Story presentation <p>Activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">-Teacher presented the story of the <i>Lovers</i>. She gave them 6 questions to answer in relation to the story. Students were called to respond. Some wrote their responses in the chat box and the teacher read their responses. She asked them questions for analyzing literary techniques. First, by asking the protagonist of the story; the characterization; the climax; the foreshadowing; the third person omniscient point of view; and the last on identifying if the story is a legend, a folktale or a romance.

- For their assignment the students will work in groups to give the summary of The Lover. They will form an illustration or a diagram or a flow chart about the story.

T-3 Topic: Palitang Turo- Minamasid

Strategies:

- Lecture-discussion using whiteboard presentation online
- Demonstration of activity with set criteria

Activities:

- Teacher presented the lesson on hagdang karanasan- Minamasid using the white board. She provided activity for the students and gave them 10 minutes to work on this then giving the criteria for rating them. After 10 minutes she asked them to present what they did. This was an interactive activity with the students.
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T-4 Topic: Ch 4- Subject of Art

Strategies:

- Lecture presentation through art interpretation
- Lecture-discussion using pictures/paintings and PowerPoint presentation online

Activities:

- The teacher gave the lecture on subject of an art and types of subjects of an art. After her lecture she again brought out the same pictures and let the students analyze the pictures according to its subject as an art and the types of subjects of an art. She appreciated the students for their responses. Then, she asked them to interpret the pictures by selecting their preference and giving why they choose the particular picture. After the students have done their analysis of the paintings the teacher asked them if they understood their lesson.
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T-5 Topic: What is the difference between moral and ethics?

Strategies:

- Lecture using PowerPoint presentation and video clip
- Lecture-Discussion

Activities:

- Teacher presented the topic of the day on the 2 philosophical theories: Teleological and Deontological. She presented the lesson using PowerPoint presentation. As she lectured, she also gave example stories and cases to illustrate her lecture. She lectured on ethical egotism, characteristics of utilitarianism, and finally on Deontology ethics and Kant's theory. She gave examples that students can understand.
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T-6 Topic: Lecture Method

Strategies:

- Student group reporting using PowerPoint presentation with the teacher's guidance

Activities:

- Students were made to do the report. Every time the reporter could not explain the topic, the teacher elucidated this. There were many subtopics related to lecture method that was reported by the student who seems to be the leader of the group. The other short topics were read by the other reporters from the PowerPoint and the teacher did the explaining. It seems that most of the interactions were done by the teacher and the reporter. Later, the teacher asked the class some questions for them to interact as well. Since most of the students cannot give their verbal
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response, the teacher allowed them to write their answers in the chat box and he just read these to the class. Two groups of reporters have finished their topics.

T-7 Topic: Balitang Isports

Strategies:

- Lecture method using PowerPoint presentation online
- Use of pictures

Activities:

-The teacher showed through the screen pictures of sports personality like Manny Pacquiao, Rafael Nepomoceno, etc (8 persons) then asked the students to identify them and give the sports they are famous of. This is a good way to keep the students engaged however the students do not know many of these sports' personality, so the teacher have to do the identifying. It could have been better if the teacher assigned the students ahead of time to make research of a sports personality and then present these to class during their meeting. After the motivation, the teacher presented the lesson on the parts of sports news and how to write one. She read some samples of sports news highlighting on what this part of the news is. After the lesson presentation, she asked if the students have questions. She then asked each one to give their favorite sports and to write a news about this. However, she did not let them write the new right there in their class, instead she dismisses them and make this activity as their assignment

T-8 Topic: Proteins and amino Acids

Strategies:

- Lecture-Discussion-Demonstration using PPT presentation online
- use of drawings of chains
- Chat quiz time; Q&A

Activities:

- She presented the new lesson on proteins and amino acids asking the students what are proteins and what is amino acid, as her motivating questions. She is very clear and articulate in her manner of presenting the lesson. She presents the functions of proteins, amino acids, acid base properties, zwitterions, classification of amino acids, etc. Aside from the pictures and illustrations of these using the PowerPoint, she also draws illustrations in the whiteboard to make her point clear. Her manner of presenting is very clear and the students could understand her because they could answer her questions. She has a way of engaging her students to respond by giving them time allotment. Her aura is such that she could engage the students to respond.

T-9 Topic: Building a people, building a nation

Strategies:

- Lecture-discussion using PowerPoint online
- Use of examples

Activities:

She presented her lecture through the PowerPoint, read the lecture then explain/discuss. To involve the students in the learning process, she let the students read the PowerPoint notes and the teacher explained and discussed giving examples to illustrate. She continued with this method of letting the students read the slides and teacher explains. The topics moved to the Preamble of the Philippines as the bases for building the character of the people, then moved to the topic on the strengths of the Filipino in terms of its value system,

then the weaknesses of the Filipinos. She asked the students to give examples of their experiences illustrating strengths and weaknesses.

T-10 Topic: Model on Game-based Learning – Fractions

Strategies:

- Lecture-discussion using PowerPoint presentation and video presentation
- student activity online- games online

Activities:

Teacher presented a video on how to facilitate a game-based strategy however; this did not work out well, so she needed someone to help her out. Later when the video was already functioning, it shows the top 10 fun games that could be utilized in Mathematics. This was presented twice for students to really get through the games. She let them work on an activity where they will have to answer 3 questions posted by the teacher. She gave them time to do this. Once they were done, the teacher asked them to give their answers for the 3 questions. She acknowledged and appreciated their responses. She then gave them an assessment tasks to work in pairs. The task is to develop a mathematical game that has instructional value following the template. The students will select from the top 10 games presented and she gave them instructions on what to do using a topic from Fractions.

T-11 Topic: Building and Enhancing New Literacies across the curriculum- Creativity Literacy

Strategies:

- Lecture-discussion integrated with various presentations e.g., slides, video clips, stories
- motivational lecture

Activities:

Teacher presented the new lesson on building and enhancing creativity and she did these with several presentations like: video clip, PPT slide, song lyrics; pictures, synopsis of a movie clip, asking questions for students to respond verbally and in their chat box, a mini-debate, etc. Obviously, the teacher engaged her students actively to sustain their interest. Her initial motivation question is; *Are you creative?* Most of the students responded “Maybe”. This same question was her ending query before she dismissed the class. She also asked the students to make a mini-debate on whether *“creativity is learned? Or inherited?”* She presented her lecture using PPT slide and discussed the topic extensively.

T-12 Topic: Technology Age

Strategies:

- Lecture-discussion using PowerPoint presentation online
- sharing ideas and examples

Activities:

The lesson for the day was presented through a PowerPoint presentation. As the lecture progresses, the teacher stay connected with the class by asking them to share their ideas. He posted reflection question that allow the students to think and give their ideas. The topic was interestingly discussed and the students were given the opportunity to reflect and discuss their ideas and opinions.

T-13 Topic: El Filibusterismo

Strategies:

- Lecture-discussion using PowerPoint presentation
-

-use of stories and narratives

Activities:

Teacher presented the new lesson on El Filibusterismo which is a sequel of Noli. As she presented the lesson, she told the excerpts of the stories and asked questions on why Rizal wrote the novel in another country; What are Rizal's experiences; what were his objectives in writing the novels; etc. Interaction between the teacher and the students were evident. Teacher appreciated the students for their responses.

T-14 Topic: Sampling and sampling procedures

Strategies:

-Lecture using PowerPoint presentation

Activities:

Teacher discussed about the topic, giving some examples where they could apply what was lectured. The teacher asked on whether the student understood the lecture as presented in the PowerPoint. All the topics were discussed and explained very well by the teacher based from the slides on the ppt. After the topics were discussed, the teacher asked if the students have queries.

T-15 Topic: Ang Huling El Bimbo

Strategies:

-Lecture discussion using the lyrics of the song

-Oral recitation of students

Activities:

-Teacher presented the new song the *El Bimbo* with its lyrics. It serves both as a motivation and the presentation of the lesson. The teacher asked the students questions related to the song like *inspirasyong sa kanta? ano ang ipinahiwatig ng kanta? Bakit sumikat and kantang ito?* She called the students to respond to her questions to encourage them to participate. Then she asked the students to choose a line or a stanza from the lyrics of the song as to what struck them. She gave them time to think and after which gave the oral recitation one by one. She thanked the students for their participation and involvement in the discussion. She asked her final question as to what the music wants to convey to our culture and problems in society.

T-16 Topic: Physical Fitness and Misconceptions related to it

Strategies:

-Lecture using PowerPoint presentation online

-Discussion; Q&A

Activities:

Teacher presented the lesson on physical fitness and the misconceptions related to these. She read from the lecture in the slides then gave examples every time she has examples. Usually, she gave real-life experiences as examples. After her lecture she asked the students questions and called them one by one. Generally, students responded in the dialect and the teacher is contented that they were able to answer and participate in the discussion. Everyone was called to recite. The lecture lasted for one hour and the remaining 30 minutes was for the question and answer regarding the lecture.

Both teacher and students are trying their best to cope with the challenges of online learning. Teachers must learn how to present their lessons via Google Meet, and injecting various techniques

would entail technical know-how and skills. There were problems along the way, considering that since they had no control over students being present in their classes, they could not have the perfect assurance that all the students were engaged in their lectures. Many students do not usually turn on their cameras, and the teacher cannot see their reactions and participation. However, gauging from their lesson presentation and styles in activating their learners, the teachers can go through the whole teaching-learning process. It is the duty of the students how they could accelerate their learning.

Students with access to technology can participate and engage in the activities presented by the teacher. Since college students today are more computer savvy, they learn faster online. Accordingly, e-learning requires 40-60% less time to learn than in the traditional class setting because students can learn at their own pace, going back and re-reading, skipping, or accelerating through concepts as they choose (weforum, 2020). Teaching and learning online would become a “stay-in” modality in presenting a lesson, especially when the hybrid strategy is employed.

Teaching –Learning Activities and Strategies Employed in the Face-To-Face Classes

After the height of the pandemic, when normalization was permeating even in the academic sector, face-to-face classes were resumed. Class observations were also resumed. The lecture method still prevails as the dominant teaching strategy based on class observations. Only, this time, is the teacher’s presence felt. In Matrices 2 and 3, the face-to-face class observations of the SED instructors for the first and second semesters of AY 2022-2023 are presented. By this time, the teachers are more familiar with integrating ICT and using PowerPoint. The teacher efficiently employs lecture-discussion and lecture demonstration. The question-and-answer technique manifests more in the lecture-discussion method, while the field demonstration and practical activities allow the students to demonstrate the skills learned. These are more illustrated in the lecture-demonstration method. Still, the lecture method is used in combination with discussion and demonstration.

Matrix 2.

Teaching-Learning strategies and activities employed by the faculty during the face-to-face class observations during the 1st semester of the academic year 2022-2023.

T-1	<p>Topic: Greenhouse gases</p> <p>Teaching Strategy- Lecture Discussion integrating ICT/PPT</p> <p>Activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teacher reviews the previous lesson specifically on the laboratory activity e.g., 2 jars of water and baking soda experiment, etc. She asks the students their observations of the experiments. • Teacher utilizes the PPT presentation showing illustration e.g., greenhouse gases and asks “what happens if there are greenhouse gases?” Students were asked to give their responses. • Teacher asks questions while doing the lecture and calls students to respond. Teacher uses practical examples that the students could relate in their day-to-day experience. • Teacher asks the students to go to their groups for the activity. The Performance task: “Trace the greenhouse gases...”.
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- Teacher shows the example on what the students are to do. She verifies if the students understood the instructions for the activity. The activity questions were flashed on the computer screen. These guide the students on what to do.
 - After 15 minutes the students were asked to go back to their seats and the group presentation was done by the students
 - The Lecture method integrating ICT/PPT presentation was evidently utilized by the teacher.
-

T-2 Topic: Logic

Teaching Strategy- Lecture-Discussion-activity

Activities:

- A brief reminder on the topic last meeting was mentioned before the teacher introduces the topic for the day which is on LOGIC
 - Teacher presents the objectives through the PPT.
 - Teacher has the students seated in their group to make them ready for the activity, she presented the work to be done and set a timer for the activity. This is to identify if the statement is True or False or sometimes True or false. This serves as a quiz for the student which synergizes them
 - Teacher used this sentence as a prelude to her lesson: *What is statement?* The topic is on Logic statements and Quantifiers
 - Teacher gives a lecture on the proponents: Leibniz and George Boole. The Logic statements like: question, command, opinion, fact was given examples and the students are to identify the statements as presented in the PPT
 - Teacher gives Seatwork #1 where they have to identify if the phrase is a *statement* or *not a statement*. Students cooperatively work in groups.
 - Then the topic on *Logic connectives and symbols* was presented and the *truth value table* were presented. Students were given examples and they also answered the activity given
 - The teacher actively engaged the students in every activity so that there is no dull moment with them.
 - The Lecture Method was vibrantly demonstrated by the teacher facilitated through PPT, activities on the board and seat work.
-

T-3 **Topic: Aerobics**

Teaching Strategy- Lecture and demonstration (carousel style)

Activities:

Part 1- Lecture

- Teacher reviews the lesson. The students were asked to discuss what they had done with their assignment on the “meal plan”
 - The teacher is alive in questioning the students and the students generally responded in visayan.
 - The teacher utilizes the PPT presentation although he did not use the projector hence the students at the back could not view what is presented.
 - The teacher presents the objectives for the lesson of the day – (on aerobics)
 - He stands and delivers the lecture moving about to give all the students the chance of viewing how he delivers using his body language.
 - The lecture includes the importance of exercise and the types of exercise
 - After the lecture, he asks the students to get ½ CW for his assessment.
-

- The teacher asks the students to move outside to the gym for the actual field demonstration on physical activities
- The Lecture Method with PPT presentation served as the strategy of the teacher prior to the field demo outside the classroom.

Part II- Field Demonstration

- Teacher already prepares the gym and the instructions are placed in in the different areas (circular position).
- The activity he labeled as Tabatha Circuit. There are listed steps for the group of students to perform. The music was also prepared in such a way that after each activity, the students perform while the music is playing. When it stops, they move to the next area just like in a carousel strategy
- The students perform as expected and teachers checks on everyone if they did the moves correctly
- Actual body movements were exhibited by the students and the carousel strategy was employed.

T-4 **Topic: Pagsusulat**
Teaching Strategy- Lecture Discussion
Activities:

- *Review of previous lesson-*
- Teacher asks the students on what they have discussed last week. She asks what they have learned.
- Teacher continues the discussion of the topic on “*diskurso*” and reminds the students on their assignment on “*uri ng diskurso*”
- *Presentation of the lesson-*
- Teacher lectures on the topic on “*pagsusulat*”. Teacher is confident and is articulate in giving her lecture. The objectives of the lesson were not articulated because the teacher continues the lesson from her asking the students the question on their previous lesson,
- Teacher groups the students to do any of the forms of what they have written in their assignment. They choose what “*sulatin*” they will write. They will do this activity the whole remaining duration of their time because they will continue the activity next meeting
- The questioning done by the teacher were mostly lower-order although there were instances when higher-order questions were raised.
- While the students are doing the activity the teacher wrote on the board the following:

Pamantayan sa pagsusulat:

- | | |
|------------------------------------|-----|
| • <i>Nilalaman</i> | 30% |
| • <i>Pagtatanaw ng mga detalye</i> | 25% |
| • <i>Kahusay pagsulat</i> | 25% |
| | 80% |

- The Lecture Method with some questionings in the lecture was exhibited by the teacher.

T-5 **Topic: Body movements**
Teaching Strategy- Lecture and demonstration
Activities:

Part I- Lecture

- Teacher lectures while sitting down, but she can capture the students' attention because of her voice and her hand actions. The way she gives a lecture is like a "mother to a child" giving instructions and directions at the same time weaving a story to elucidate her examples and giving advises to them particularly in grooming, health, personality, etc.
- She "code-switches" in her presentation of the lecture with examples clearly articulated in visayan as though she was an adviser as to how students should behave, perform, and exude themselves.
- The examples given are often practical and relatable to the students, sometimes calling on individual students to illustrate the example.
- Teacher integrates the core values of SIC but also injects her own perceptions/opinions on what students should do in the future e.g., "*do not marry yet. Work after you graduate..2 years in the Philippines, after these service work abroad to earn more and help your parents, buy a house, buy a car, etc...enjoy life while young....*
- Some examples and advises were practical and down-to-earth telling the students the consequences of their actions, e.g., what will happen if the students do not obey... do the opposite on what they are taught or told to do....
- After the lecture, the teacher asks the students to move outside to the gym for the actual field demonstration on physical activities
- The Lecture teaching strategy where most of the talking and discussion was done by the teacher.

Part II- Field Demonstration

- Teacher gives instructions for students to demonstrate. She demonstrates the particular moves and the students follow
- The teacher shows enthusiasm in the actual performance, exhibiting the moves actively and effectively
- The students perform as expected and teachers checks on everyone if they did the moves correctly
- Actual field performance was done by the students through the instruction of the teacher.

T-6

Topic: Theories of interpersonal relationships

Teaching Strategy- Eclectic/Varied Strategies – Lecture using PPT, Video Clip, Cooperative Group Learning, Discussion

Activities:

- Teacher lets the students sit in a circular position to review on the previous lesson. She prepared a box where questions written in a slip of paper are rolled for the students to answer. A music was played such that when the music stops, the student holding the box will pick one question to answer this. After the student responded and the teacher approving of the answer, the music is played again and the box is passed around. This goes on until all the questions were uncovered.
 - The questions raised were mostly HOTS e.g. *What are the types of relationships, Explain the theory of love, explain why transparency is important,*
-

Why is there a need for internal relationship, What do you mean by interpersonal relations, why interpersonal relation is important.

- Teacher presents the new topic on *Theories of Interpersonal relationships*. She presents the objectives through PPT.
 - Teacher raises the question: *In what ways can interpersonal relationship enduring or brief?* The theory on *uncertainty reduction theory* was presented. A video clip was shown by the teacher, after which she raises HOTS questions for students to answer/discuss.
 - Teacher gives an activity for the students to perform. She gives them 15 minutes to work on the activity. Each student has to work on one activity question.
 - The next theory –*social exchange theory* - was presented through a video. Again, the teacher raises a HOTS question. Two groups were formed for the next activity where they will write their responses in a sheet of manila paper. The column on: *Theory- Cost- Benefit* were asked. While the students worked on the activity, the teacher moved about to check on their responses.
 - Teacher exhibited the versatility of the lecture method by integrating other strategies in the presentation. There was no dull moment during the presentation and time management was observed.
-

T-7 **Topic: CPR**

Teaching Strategy- Lecture Demonstration

Activities:

- Teacher lectures on: The characteristics of a good first-aider; how to check on the CABG; when the best time to give a CPR is. Fluency of communication is evident in the lecture. The objectives were not stated specifically as the teacher seems to embed this in her discussion.
 - Teacher demonstrates step-by-step on how to do the CPR using the pillow as its IMs.
 - Teacher asks questions whether the students understood the lecture-demonstration on how to do the CPR
 - Teacher asks the students to do a return-demonstration. She asks for volunteers, then later assign them by pairs and rates their performance, if the followed the step-by-step process
 - The lecture method was used to demonstrate the activity. Instructions were given by the teacher for the students to make a return-demo on what she lectured.
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T-8 **Topic: Types of Personality**

Teaching Strategy- Lecture using PPT & student's discussion based from their responses in the personality Assessment that they took

Activities:

- Teacher asks the students to recap what they have learned last meeting on the different intelligences.
 - In opening the next topic, the teacher asks the students whether they have taken the 16 personality tests.
 - Teacher presents the new topic on *Types of Personality*. He presents the objectives through PPT.
 - Teacher presents each personality type, giving its characteristics, the advantages and disadvantages through PPT presentations.
-

Teaching-Learning Strategies and Activities Employed by College Instructors in their Online and Face-to-face Classes

- After the lecture and discussion, he asks who among the students represent this type of personality and ask them to explain why.
 - This type of discussion follows the same pattern where teacher presents the type of personality, gives the characteristics, advantages, and disadvantages; then asks the students as to who has this personality type and explain why.
 - The lecture method was enthusiastically exhibited by the teacher making use of the PPT and questioning techniques.
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Matrix 3.

Teaching-learning strategies and activities employed by the faculty during the face-to-face class observations during the 2nd semester of the academic year 2022-2023.

- | | |
|---------------|--|
| Instructor-1 | <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Strategy used- <i>Lecture using PPT presentation; Activities were used to facilitate the lecture.</i>• Topic: Information Society• Teacher Activities-<ul style="list-style-type: none">➤ The teacher presents the activity in the PPT with a statement having a blank in it. The students will guess the answer to the blank. When the answer is deciphered, the teacher praised the students, then discuss the concept in relation to the topic on information and communication.➤ Each concept is presented through this activity, where students fill-in the blank by supplying the answer to the blank, then this becomes the focal concept to be discussed. The only challenge in the presentation is on the color of the font used in the PPT because the color is white and the background is light, hence it could not easily be read at the back.➤ The activity which has the response on reliability was enhanced with students identifying which information is reliable or not. This was done similar to a carousel brainstorming style where the students move from one info sheet at a time and determine its reliability. This is good because the students are able to make decisions and discernment as to the truthfulness of the information.➤ Teacher presented a video clip on the evolution of technology. |
| Instructor -2 | <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Strategy used- <i>Lecture with ICT integration</i>• Topic: Lesson Planning/Learning Plan• Teacher Activities-<ul style="list-style-type: none">➤ Teacher presented a warm-up activity- Wheel of fortune Names, where the student's name is identified after the wheel is turned. The name identified will have to respond to a question prepared by the teacher, giving a True or False answer then justify the answer. This activity caused excitement from the students. The questions were all in relation to prior knowledge on Lesson planning, as this is the teacher's way of diagnosing how far the students have the idea on Lesson Planning.➤ Presentation of the topic, stated with the question: What is a Lesson Plan? How is this different or similar with the Learning Plan? The teacher discussed the topic at the same time asked HOTS and LOTS questions. |
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- As the teacher presents the discussion of the topic in the PPT she asked the students one at a time to read what is in the PPT, then another one would give his understanding and insight on what was read.
 - The teacher advised students on what to do and what they should do when they become teachers, based from her own experiences and examples. She told them that importance of Preparation; Time consciousness; utilizing time to full advantage; learning from the trainings in school; evaluating one's own performance. Teachers should ask their students to evaluate their teaching both the negative and positive ones. From her example, she asked students to write o her and tell her their evaluation of her teaching.
 - The topics discussed and presented in the PPT include:
 - Nine important events in instruction; what should be included in the lesson Plan
 - Types of Lesson plan, i.e detailed, semi-detailed, and understanding by design although the emphasis centered in the first 2 types
 - Parts of a Lesson Plan – which include objectives, Subject Matter; Procedure; Evaluation, and Assignment
 - Why is Lesson Planning important? What are the challenges encountered in the teaching of Social Studies?
 - Components of the Lesson Plan, e.g. Title, Date; Objectives; Standards; Plans or Lesson; Assessment; Homework; Cross Curriculum; Integration; Differentiation, Technology; assessment
-

Instructor -3

- Strategy used- ***Lecture using activities via PPT and board work activities***
 - Topic: **Differentiating Functions: The Chain Rule; Higher-Order Derivative; Differentiating Common Functions**
 - Teacher Activities-
 - Teacher presents the problems for students to solve/work on as a group. They placed their answers in the sheets that the teacher provides earlier. The problem is presented in the PPT, but the font is rather small to be seen at the back, although the students have clear eyesight to see these.
 - After the group solve the problem, they raised their solutions up for the teacher to check and tally the correct responses of the students by groups. This serves as the motivation for students to engage themselves in the activity
 - Teacher is encouraging and engaging such that the students are not afraid of Math
 - Teacher is so dynamic and alive, although she's so fast in her explanations and solutions to the problems.
 - Teacher gave more problems for students to solve and asked volunteers to solve in the board.
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Instructor -4

- Strategy used- ***Lecture integrating ICT and physical activities & Field Demonstration***
 - Topic: **Basic Human Movements**
 - Teacher Activities- (Lecture portion)
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- Teacher presented a video clip on human movements via the PPT as his motivational technique
- Teacher presented the objectives for the day asking the students to read these from the PPT presentation. He then presents the topic with a question: *What is Movement?*
- He asked the students to give their ideas after which he did the lecture illustrating these with visuals in the PPT and gestures of his body.
- He asked the participation of the students by asking them to read the lecture notes presented in the PPT
- After the lecture, he gave the students an activity on describing the movement and demonstrating this to the class

Demonstration Portion

- The teacher asked the students to form 2 groups. He demonstrated the physical movements like in a relay, and asked the group to perform after his demonstration.
- The students performed the activity but their performance did not really follow all the steps that the teacher demonstrated as they were concerned as to who will finished first.
- After the group performance, the teacher asked them to perform individually and the rubric on the amount of time spent to finish the complete round was used. Teacher timed the students and informed them on their performance.
- After all had individually performed, the teacher commends those who finished the fastest

Instructor -5

- Strategy used- ***Lecture Method - using traditional technique of posting written materials on the board and asking the students to read in chorus, then asking questions.***
- Topic: ***Uri ng Bangtas ayon sa tungkulin***
- Teacher Activities-
 - Teacher posted the prepared written materials on the board while students waited for the teacher to finish the posting of all the *Uri ng Bangtas. (Paturol, Patanong, Pandamdang, Pautos, Pakiusap)*. She made use of the bond paper to print the materials. After all the materials were posted, she asked the students to orally read these in chorus. For every *Bangtas*, there is one example statement, and the students also read the example.
 - The students were asked to match the sentence to the appropriate *bantas* although it was the teacher who physically transferred the papers so they will match. After all the examples were matched the students read the materials orally in chorus as instructed by the teacher.
 - The teacher asked the students to have a group work activity. The groups were given a picture and the students were told to describe the picture using the sentences with their *bantas*.

Instructor - 6

- Strategy used- Lecture *using notes & Field Demonstration*
- Topic: **Physical Fitness**
- Teacher Activities-
 - Teacher presented her lecture as she read from her notes.
 - She is articulate in her communication and she used her voice effectively.
 - She is very confident and has a good sense of humor in her examples. She exudes a very happy disposition and this is radiated in her aura.
 - There is a part of her lecture where there are actions to be executed, and she executed these to the class. She could have asked the students to execute these as well.
 - After her lecture, she gave the students a seatwork activity on identifying the names of the positions in the pictures.

Physical activity (Demonstration portion)

- The teacher asked the students to go to their groups.
- She demonstrates the different physical activity for each of the group for them to execute. Once they know their steps, she played the music and asked them to perform.

Instructor -7

- Strategy used- *Eclectic Method- Using Lecture, PPT presentation, Games, Activities, Video Clip, Think-Pair-Share*
- Topic: **Weakness of the Filipino Character**
- Teacher Activities-
 - Teacher presented the objectives of the lesson.
 - Introduced the *Pinoy Henyo* game as her motivation and icebreaker
 - Teacher showed mastery of the lesson, speaks clearly and articulately.
 - She showed confidence and is calm in her presentation.
 - She explained the topics clearly and gives examples in the presentation
 - Values integration is inherent in the lesson
 - A video clip on the weaknesses of the Filipino character was shown. Teacher discussed the topic to the class and gave examples.
 - Activity: Think-pair-share was done on the Filipino weaknesses of character, after which the students were made to report. Teacher supplemented the report done by the students and gave practical examples.
 - Cooperative Group work Activity: 2 groups will write in the Manila Paper the weakness of the Filipino Character and the effective ways to solve these. They work in groups based on the identified weaknesses. The time allocated for the activity was 15 minutes. After they have finished their work, the group presented the results to the class.

Teaching-Learning Strategies and Activities Employed by College Instructors in their Online and Face-to-face Classes

- Instructor -8
- Strategy used- Lecture *using graphs*
 - Topic: **Isoquant & Isocost (Graphing)**
 - Teacher Activities-
 - Teacher introduced the terms Isoquant and Isocost. She defined the terms and discussed its used in Economics
 - The lesson/hypothetical data last meeting was carried over in today's lesson in terms of graphing the data.
 - The teacher asked volunteers to do the graphing illustrating the marginal product, total product, average product.
 - She then asked the students to interpret and explain the graph.
 - Teacher presents situations for students to give the interpretation and implication in business and economics.
 - Teacher lectured on the properties of the Isoquant showing illustrations printed in sheets of paper. It could have been better if this was presented in the PPT as there is a board computer in the classroom.
-
- Instructor -9
- Strategy used- *Lecture using stories*
 - Topic: **The Lovers by Bessie Head**
 - Teacher Activities-
 - Teacher introduced the autobiography of the author Besse Head. She read what is shown in the PPT as the write-up has very small font size; she emphasized the importance of narrative rather than the character.
 - Teacher discussed the story together with the students highlighting on:
 - Understanding the story*, where she gave guide questions and students were asked to give their responses
 - Analyzing literary techniques*, where she highlighted on foreshadowing, theme of the story, and relating the story's tribal practices to the current practices especially those of the tribes in Bukidnon as the city is celebrating the Kaamulan festivities.
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- Instructor -10
- Strategy used-*Lecture –Discussion Method*
 - Topic: **Integrating Media in the Curriculum**
 - Teacher Activities-
 - Teacher presented the lecture with confidence and vibrancy.
 - Statement of objectives was not presented verbally but are inherently embedded in the topics presented
 - Teacher showed mastery of the lesson, speaks clearly and articulately but is quite fast in the presentation of the lecture.
 - He explained the topics clearly and gives examples in his presentation
 - Values integration was not verbally elucidated but the presentation of the teacher could somehow illustrate the value of character and discipline, as well as social responsibility in the use of media
 - LOTS and HOTS were utilized in the process of questioning the students as to their understanding of the topics
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- Important questions raised by the teacher that could elicit critical and creative thinking:
 - How does one evaluate media if this is legit?
 - How does one examine the truth/veracity in advertisements?
 - Cite the use of Media in the different subject areas?
 - What is the important role of media literacy?
 - How do you assess/evaluate digital literacy?
 - Can you summarize/narrate what learning you have today?
-

In the face-to-face classes, it was evident that the teachers engaged their students in strategies appropriate for the lesson and objectives. One advantage when students are in the face-to-face classroom is that their engagement and participation are visible and genuinely manifested. The same is true with the teacher's verbal and non-verbal communication. The teachers demonstrate these and are visible and factual.

Categorization of the Teaching-Learning Activities Employed During Online Classes Based on the Learning Theories

Matrix 4 categorizes activities according to the theories postulated by the constructivists, the behaviorists, and the cognitivists. The constructivists construct their perspectives of the world from individual experiences and internal knowledge. It is based on how individuals interpret and create the meaning of their experiences. It is focused on prior knowledge and learning synthesis on new understanding. Behaviorists highlight observable behaviors and discount any independent mental activity. It is based on the concept of stimulus and response. It is focused on observable behaviors. The cognitivist explains how humans' minds work while they learn. It is based on mental processes and is focused on mental activities and processes.\.

Matrix 4.

*Categorization of the teaching-learning activities employed during the **ONLINE** class delivery **AY 2020-2021.***

Teaching-Learning Categories	Strategies	Activities
1. Constructivist <i>Constructivism is a teaching-learning theory where individuals construct their perspectives of the world from individual experiences and internal knowledge; Based on how individuals interpret and create the meaning of their experiences Focuses on prior knowledge and learning synthesis on new understanding</i>	T-1 Lecture using video clips	S-1 Audio listening to musical pieces of different music composition Students were asked on the movement of the music, tempo, notes played, and expression
	T-8 Lecture-Discussion-Demonstration using PPT presentation	S-8 draw illustrations on the whiteboard for a clear presentation
	T-9 Lecture-discussion using PowerPoint and examples	S-9 Students give examples of their experiences citing the strengths and weaknesses

Teaching-Learning Strategies and Activities Employed by College Instructors in their Online and Face-to-face Classes

	T-11 Lecture using varied techniques like video clip/PPT, song lyrics, mini debate, creative literacy	S-11 students construct their ideas on the mini debate on whether they are born creative or not
	T-12 –Lecture-Discussion	S-12 Students construct knowledge and share their ideas on what they think are the characteristics in the technological age
	T-15 Lecture-discussion using PPT and lyrics of the song	S-15 Students construct ideas on what struck them in the lines of the lyric of the son on <i>Ang Huling El Bimbo</i>
	T-16 Lecture Discussion	S-16 Students shared their ideas on what are their misconceptions about physical fitness and give examples
2. Behaviorist <i>Behaviorism is a teaching-learning theory that focuses on observable behaviors and discounts any independent mental activity; Based on the concept of stimulus and response Focuses on observable behaviors</i>	T-3 Lecture-discussion with presentation on the whiteboard	S-3 The activity was given to the students for them to work on and demonstrate their output
	T-6 Lecture using PowerPoint presentation with the teacher’s guidance	S-6 Students reported the topics of the lecture
	T-7 Lecture method using pictures in the PowerPoint presentation	S-7 Students write a sports news and identify the parts
	T-10 Lecture-discussion using PowerPoint presentation and video presentation	S-10 Students played games related to the topic online
3. Cognitivist <i>Cognitivism is a broad teaching-learning theory that explains how humans’ mind work while they learn; Based on mental processes Focuses on mental activities and processes</i>	T-2 Lecture using PowerPoint	S-2 Story presentation then teacher asked questions where the students wrote their responses on the chat box
	T-4 Lecture-discussion using pictures/paintings and PowerPoint presentation online	S-4 Students analyze the pictures according to its subject as an art and the types of subjects as an art; ask the students of their choice of picture and why the particular choice cuing them from the things that they learned from the lesson.

T-5 Lecture-Discussion using PowerPoint presentation and video clip	S-5 Students gave Examples of stories and cases
T-11 Lecture using varied techniques like video clip/PPT, song lyrics, mini debate, creative literacy	S-11 Students analyze the video clip presentation and the lyrics of the song
T-13 Lecture-Discussion using PPT	S-13 Students answered the questions raised by the teacher on <i>Noli Me Tangere</i>
T-14 Lecture discussion using PPT	S-14 Students answered questions on what is sampling and sampling procedure
T-15 Lecture-discussion using PPT and lyrics of the song	S-15 Students answered questions on the lyrics of the son on <i>Ang Huling El Bimbo</i>
T-16 Lecture Discussion using PPT	S-16 Student answered questions on the topic on misconceptions about physical fitness

It is observed that Teachers 1, 8,9,11,12,15, and 16 were more inclined to be constructivists as they allowed their students to construct their ideas about the topics discussed. The teachers provide cues and opportunities for students to create and interpret meanings from the discussions and lectures. They give the interpretation of musical pieces, illustrations, examples from experiences, ideas for debate, and what struck them from their learning. A learning and teaching activity enables students to engage with a teacher to learn the knowledge or skills required to achieve the desired educational outcome (Flinders University,2022)

Teachers 3,6,7, and 10 have more tendencies to be behaviorists. They provided activities where the students worked on and demonstrated their output, reported on the topics they were assigned, wrote sports news, identified the parts of the news, and played online video games related to the topic. These activities are more about observable behaviors, one characteristic of a behaviorist ideology.

Teachers 2,4,5,11, 13, 14,15, and 16 showed leanings towards being cognitivists. The activities they employed are based on mental processes and are focused on mental activities since they require the students to answer their questions based on what they presented. This is observed by most college teachers because they are focused on the cognitive knowledge that the students gain from their lectures. This is also the basis of the questions they give during assessments like quizzes and long exams.

Teaching-Learning Strategies and Activities Employed by College Instructors in their Online and Face-to-face Classes

Teachers who employed varied techniques in their lectures were likely to demonstrate the cognitive and constructivist types of teaching and learning. Sometimes, they could even use the behaviorist type as well. This is because the activities they gave are also varied and could employ constructing knowledge, involving mental processes, and performing the activities. Versatile teachers can help students develop all three types of learning as they shift from one technique to the other.

Categorization of the Teaching-Learning Activities Employed During Face-To-Face Classes Based on the Learning Theories

Matrices 5 and 6 show the categorization of the teaching-learning activities during the face-to-face class delivery in the first and second semesters of the AY 2022-2023. Since this time, the delivery of the lesson is accurate and actual, with both teacher and students interacting face-to-face, one can observe the student's engagement and participation in the lesson. Actual teacher-student interaction is evident.

It was observed in the 1st semester; only eight classes were observed, while ten classes were observed in the 2nd semester. From the observed classes in the 1st semester, two teachers demonstrated the constructivist approach, allowing the students to construct/write an essay and, in the group activity, asking them to construct their report. In the 2nd semester, one teacher asked the students to construct lyrics and music based on the story of "The Lovers" and made their interpretation. Constructivist learning is based on how individuals interpret and create the meaning of their experiences. They share ideas during the think-pair-share. It is focused on prior knowledge and learning synthesis on new understanding, and these were manifested in the lessons of T-4, T-6, I-7, and I-9.

Matrix 5.

Categorization of the teaching-learning activities employed during the FACE-TO-FACE class delivery First semester 2022-2023.

Teaching-Learning Categories	Strategies	Activities
1. Constructivist <i>Constructivism is a teaching-learning theory where individuals construct their perspectives of the world from individual experiences and internal knowledge;</i> <i>Based on how individuals interpret and create the meaning of their experiences</i> <i>Focuses on prior knowledge and learning synthesis on new understanding</i>	T-4 Lecture discussion	S-4 Students write their essay
	T-6 Eclectic Method- Lecture using PPT; Use of Video Clip; Cooperative Group	S-6 Students in the cooperative group construct their report
2. Behaviorist <i>• Behaviorism is a teaching-learning theory that focuses on observable behaviors and</i>	T-1 Lecture discussion integrating ICT/PPT	S-1 Students trace the greenhouse gas effect
	T-3 Lecture Demonstration	

<i>discounts any independent mental activity;</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Based on the concept of stimulus and response</i> • <i>Focuses on observable behaviors</i> 	T-5 Lecture Demonstration	S-3 Students perform the aerobics activity using the carousel style
	T-7 Lecture-Demonstration	S-5 Students perform the field demonstration
		S-7 Students demonstrate how to do the CPR
3. Cognitivist <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Cognitivism is a broad teaching-learning theory that explains how humans' mind work while they learn;</i> • <i>Based on mental processes</i> • <i>Focuses on mental activities and processes</i> 	T-2 Lecture-Discussion	S-2 Students identify what is a statement and what is not; they fill-in the table on truth value chart
	T-6 Eclectic method using PPT, Video clip, cooperative group	S-6 Responded to questions and answer portion raised by the teacher
	T-8 Lecture Discussion	S-8 students assess their type of personality; give the advantage and disadvantage on the type of personality they possess

The behaviorist approach was evident in the face-to-face classes, as one can observe that the students performed the activities required of them individually or in groups. In the 1st semester, Teachers 1, 3, 5, and 7 asked their students to trace the flow of the greenhouse gas effect, perform the aerobics activity using the carousel style, perform the field demonstration, and demonstrate how to do the CPR. These activities are all requiring actual performance from the students. In the 2nd semester, Instructors 3, 4,6, and 8 allowed their students to solve problems in the seats and on the board; performed physical activities on body movements; did the actual physical movements demonstrated by the instructor; and graphed the isoquant and isocost in the Economics class. The Physical Education teachers generally practiced the behaviorist approach in their field activities or practical applications. These activities are more focused on performance, which shows observable behaviors. It is learning by doing, which is a behaviorist perspective of learning.

Matrix 6.

*Categorization of the teaching-learning activities employed during the **FACE-TO-FACE** class delivery **Second Semester AY 2022-2023.***

Teaching-Learning Categories	Strategies	Activities
1. Constructivist <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Constructivism is a teaching-learning theory where individuals construct their perspectives of the</i> 	I-9 Lecture using stories	S-9 students constructed lyrics and music based from the story on The Lovers and performed this in the class

Teaching-Learning Strategies and Activities Employed by College Instructors in their Online and Face-to-face Classes

<p><i>world from individual experiences and internal knowledge;</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Based on how individuals interpret and create the meaning of their experiences</i> • <i>Focuses on prior knowledge and learning synthesis on new understanding</i> 	<p>I-7 Eclectic Method using games, activities, video clips, think-pair-share</p>	<p>S-7 students construct ideas during the think-share-pair group activity</p>
<p>2. Behaviorist</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Behaviorism is a teaching-learning theory that focuses on observable behaviors and discounts any independent mental activity;</i> • <i>Based on the concept of stimulus and response</i> • <i>Focuses on observable behaviors</i> 	<p>I-3 Lecture using activities via PPT and board work activities</p>	<p>S-3students solve problems in the seats and on the board</p>
<td data-bbox="619 775 975 837"> <p>I-4 Lecture integrating ICT and field demonstration</p> </td> <td data-bbox="1002 775 1348 882"> <p>S-4 Students performed physical activities on body movements</p> </td>	<p>I-4 Lecture integrating ICT and field demonstration</p>	<p>S-4 Students performed physical activities on body movements</p>
<td data-bbox="619 920 975 983"> <p>I-6 Lecture using Notes and field activities</p> </td> <td data-bbox="1002 920 1348 983"> <p>S-6 Students performed physical activities</p> </td>	<p>I-6 Lecture using Notes and field activities</p>	<p>S-6 Students performed physical activities</p>
<td data-bbox="619 1021 975 1084"> <p>I-8 Lecture using graphs</p> </td> <td data-bbox="1002 1021 1348 1084"> <p>S-8 students graphed the isoquant and isocost</p> </td>	<p>I-8 Lecture using graphs</p>	<p>S-8 students graphed the isoquant and isocost</p>
<p>3. Cognitivist</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Cognitivism is a broad teaching-learning theory that explains how humans' mind work while they learn;</i> • <i>Based on mental processes</i> • <i>Focuses on mental activities and processes</i> 	<p>I- 1 Lecture using PPT</p>	<p>S-1 students fill-in the blanks in the activity presented in the PPT</p>
<td data-bbox="619 1245 975 1384"> <p>I-2 Lecture integrating ICT-PPT, wheel of names, games, discussion, examples</p> </td> <td data-bbox="1002 1245 1348 1308"> <p>S- 2 Students answered the Question on Lesson Planning</p> </td>	<p>I-2 Lecture integrating ICT-PPT, wheel of names, games, discussion, examples</p>	<p>S- 2 Students answered the Question on Lesson Planning</p>
<td data-bbox="619 1424 975 1532"> <p>I-5 Lecture method using the traditional approach and cooperative group work</p> </td> <td data-bbox="1002 1424 1348 1532"> <p>S-5 Students answered the group activity presented by the teacher</p> </td>	<p>I-5 Lecture method using the traditional approach and cooperative group work</p>	<p>S-5 Students answered the group activity presented by the teacher</p>
<td data-bbox="619 1570 975 1677"> <p>I-7 Eclectic Method using games, activities, video clips, think-pair-share</p> </td> <td data-bbox="1002 1570 1348 1733"> <p>S-7students described the video chips based from the criteria in the lecture; share ideas during the think-pair-share</p> </td>	<p>I-7 Eclectic Method using games, activities, video clips, think-pair-share</p>	<p>S-7students described the video chips based from the criteria in the lecture; share ideas during the think-pair-share</p>
<td data-bbox="619 1783 975 1845"> <p>I-9 Lecture using stories; making song lyrics and tune</p> </td> <td data-bbox="1002 1783 1348 1845"> <p>S-9 Discuss on the story on The Lovers</p> </td>	<p>I-9 Lecture using stories; making song lyrics and tune</p>	<p>S-9 Discuss on the story on The Lovers</p>
<td data-bbox="619 1883 975 1912"> <p>I-10 Lecture Discussion</p> </td> <td data-bbox="1002 1883 1348 1982"> <p>S-10 Responded to the questions of the teacher pertaining to the lesson</p> </td>	<p>I-10 Lecture Discussion</p>	<p>S-10 Responded to the questions of the teacher pertaining to the lesson</p>

The cognitivist approach focused more on mental activities and processes. In the 1st semester, this was practiced by Teachers 2, 6, and 8 by letting their students identify what is a statement and what is not and letting them fill in the table on the truth value chart. Students were also asked to respond to questions the teacher raised about the topics discussed. Students were made to describe their personality type, as this was given to them as an assignment in the previous class. They also give the advantages and disadvantages of the type of personality they possess based on their readings in their assignment. In the 2nd semester, Instructors 1, 2, 5, 7, 9, and 10 demonstrated that they were cognitivists in their approach to teaching. They let students fill in the blanks in the activity presented in the PPT and answer the questions on the topic in Lesson Planning and the group activity. They also describe the video clips according to what was discussed. They described the story on “The Lovers” and responded to the questions raised by the instructor. It could be deduced that the teachers were more cognitivist in their approach because they designed their lesson delivery to match their cognitive objectives and in the manner in which the students will be assessed, especially since they are to take the licensure exam for teachers, which is more cognitivist in approach.

Similar observations are noted in both the online and face-to-face classes; college teachers are more cognitivists in their approach. Teachers who employ varied techniques in their lectures demonstrate the cognitive and constructivist types of teaching and learning. Their varied activities allow the students to construct knowledge involving mental processes. It could be deduced that College teachers expect students to accumulate cognitive knowledge from their lectures because they will need this when they take the licensure exam.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The teaching and learning strategies and activities employed by the college instructors at San Isidro College were analyzed and categorized according to the popular theories of constructivists, behaviorists, and cognitivists. Thirty-five online and face-to-face lessons were explored, and from these lessons, the predominant teaching strategy is the lecture method enhanced by varying techniques to make it more appealing to the students. Often, college teachers do a combination of lecture-discussion supplemented by ICT integration, PowerPoint presentation, and other interactive techniques like the use of video clips, stories, illustrations, news items, pictures, games, music, carousel brainstorming, think-pair-share, graphing, and problem-solving. They also utilized lecture demonstration through performance and by doing the activities.

Categorizing the activities utilized by the instructors in their lessons showed that it was apparent that these activities were more attuned to the cognitivist approach to teaching. Cognitivists address the issue of how information is received, organized, stored, and retrieved by the mind. Cognitivism concentrates on the mental activities of the learner that lead up to a response and acknowledges the process of mental planning, goal setting, and organizational strategies (cited in (Shuell, 1986; Science et al., 2018). It directs student thought processes and interactions with the materials (cited in (Ertmer & Newby, 1993; Science et al., 2018). Learning is described as changes in states of knowledge rather than changes in the probability of responding. College instructors are more prone to adopt the cognitivist teaching and learning approach to help students learn what they are supposed to and to increase their learning opportunities. College instructors should be adept with teaching-learning theories to help them become versatile teachers

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who could provide transformative learning to students. After all, the skill in shifting their teaching strategies and activities to conform with the constructivist, behaviorist, and cognitivist approaches have their breakthrough advantages in the holistic development of the learners.

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